

**From Displacement to Staying
Methodological and empirical challenges
in studying those who deliberately remain in wartime Ukraine**

Research Project Description

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Problem statement

In dialogue with European colleagues while doing research in Ukraine and about Ukraine, I constantly encounter an ambivalence between what foreigners expect war to be and what actually happens here. War, they assume, means total disruption – fear, trauma, survival mode. Yet in Ukraine, normal life continues paradoxically alongside all this. Unique things happen – even miracles. How we stand in this unequal war. How we crowdfund armies and volunteer. How

military research and development accelerates. How we make drones in garages. How businesses don't just survive but grow. How art and literature boom.

But maybe the most exciting thing – the one underlying and making possible everything else – is staying itself. People remain in their cities, in their homes, in their communities while war unfolds around them. All these miracles depend on this staying and start with it.

This may seem obvious – and it indeed is. So obvious that most research overlooks it entirely. Scholarship focuses on mobility, migration, displacement, refugees. Staying appears as mere absence of action, a residual category for those left behind. My project addresses this blind spot by developing the figure of *the Stayer* – a conceptual counterpart to the classical sociological Stranger – and investigates their social role and functions empirically based on the corpus of relevant fragments from Ukrainian civilians' diaries.

This focus on staying is lately emerging in other contexts – in disaster sociology, migration studies, climate and urbanization research – but nowhere as vividly as in Ukraine. We have films, TV series, books, massive empirical research explicitly addressing this phenomenon – although naming it in different ways.

I think in our unstable era of multiple crises, Ukraine is not unique here. We are just first. The Denkraum Ukraine's website slogan, "Uniting through knowledge about Ukraine," gains even stronger sense in this light: the figure of *the Stayer*, developed through Ukrainian experience, offers an analytical category that reshapes how we understand social life under massive ongoing disruption.

In fact, I conduct this research exactly because I am a Stayer. Since 2014, when war began in my native Donetsk, I have remained in Ukraine – first in occupied territories, then in Kyiv. This is not just a methodological necessity like access to local literature or taking interviews. This is more about an existential choice: to study staying, I must stay – maintain continuous presence, embeddedness in ongoing social life, access to shifting experiences as they unfold. Doing genuine war studies from comfortable distance is tempting yet hardly possible – especially in a phenomenological register, as I do. Leaving would transform me into a Stranger studying all this from outside – and my research would become impossible.

Broader project

The project I seek funding for is an integral part of my doctoral dissertation I expect to defend in 2027. The dissertation develops the abovementioned social-phenomenological framework of the *Stayer* to analyze collective staying under conditions of massive and durable disruptions, such as wars.

The dissertation makes two **theoretical contributions**. First, it introduces the Stayer as an ontological inversion of the sociological figure of the Stranger and relocates estrangement from displacement and detachment from one's community to collective remaining in place while the shared world transforms. Second, it offers an epistemological re-specification of Schutzian

sociology of knowledge, challenging its implicit assumption that everyday knowledge presupposes a stable world and showing how everyday knowledge, meaning, and social intelligibility are maintained when familiar worlds are destabilized and everyday life is continuously ruptured across multiple dimensions.

These inversions are grounded empirically through analysis of Ukrainian civilians' wartime diaries.

Conceived in the beginning of 2025, this broader project has already been presented at 5 international conferences and summer schools and 3 invited talks at the universities of Vienna and Warsaw. It has received an extended review and positive assessment from Prof. Andrzej Waśkiewicz, a leading theorist of the Stranger tradition in Poland.

Different parts of the project have been supported by competitive funding from the Polish National Agency for Academic Exchange (NAWA), the Institute for Human Sciences in Vienna (IWM), Center for Subjectivity Research at the University of Copenhagen, German Society for Phenomenological Research, and Graduate School for Social Research (Polish Academy of Sciences).

Doctoral research is currently at a stage where the theoretical framework is finalized and being prepared for publication, while the empirical analysis has advanced through a completed pilot study.

Planned activities

Within this broader framework, the project I seek funding to finalize and submit for publication the empirical-methodological component of my dissertation. This article makes several **methodological and empirical contributions**.

First, it demonstrates a two-level *operationalization strategy*: object-level criteria defining who counts as a Stayer under which conditions, and process-level operationalization showing how sense-making and knowledge maintenance become empirically observable.

Second, it elaborates on the *corpus of diaries fragments* that directly articulate remaining in place, maintaining everyday life, and negotiating belonging and normality under war conditions. The curated corpus inventory will be made openly available on the Stayer project website allowing other researchers to reuse, reinterpret, and extend the empirical material under different theoretical perspectives, with different methods, and as applied to different empirical cases.

Third, it discusses *wartime diaries as sociological data* and analyses how theory-driven and iterative qualitative coding can be combined to analyze complex, non-standardized narrative data, allowing analytical categories derived from social theory to be refined through sustained engagement with empirical material.

Finally, it develops a *coding approach* using MAXQDA to capture ambivalence, co-occurrence, and tension, enabling multiple analytical dimensions (such as normality and catastrophe,

belonging and estrangement) to be traced within narrative segments, showing how qualitative data analysis can trace meaning-making practices in complex, non-standardized narrative data.

Expected deliverables

I plan to submit this article to *Qualitative Research* (ISSN: 1468-7941).

Beyond academic publication, I will share methodological insights through the MAXQDA blog, which publishes detailed accounts of research design and coding processes, allowing space for practical details typically excluded from scholarly journals.

Empirical findings will also be published on the *project website* (<http://stay.in.ua>) and potentially through broadly accessible platform (my priority is *The Sociological Review* magazine).

The fellowship will support essential stages of manuscript preparation: professional proofreading and editorial consultation by a native English speaker to ensure publication-ready quality, potential article processing fees, and MAXQDA subscription.

These series of publications are based on the report on my pilot study presented at my doctoral school and publicly accessible via the project's repository:

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18040135>.